

TERMINOLOGY AS AN FIELD OF STRUCTURAL LINGUISTICS

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ANNOTATION

The fact that the fields of linguistics and terminology are closely related to each other is based on words and their meanings. This article discusses the fact that terminology is a branch of structural linguistics and several researches that have been done and need to be done in it.

KEY WORDS: term, terminology, business, lexicon, term, terminology, derivational speech

Questions about the importance of business and business terms in the daily lifestyle and activities of people around the world are increasing. This is the reason for the development of new business directions and business lexicon in this area. As a result, it is not an exaggeration to say that business terminology with the characteristics of a national language has emerged in each country. The above factors created the need to study business terminology from the point of view of linguistics, to systematize and organize terms and lexical units. The close interdependence of language and society, their dynamic and continuous changes, as well as the regular acquisition and widespread use of new terms and lexical units in the field require constant research in this matter.

The comparative-typological analysis of business terms and lexemes in world linguistics on the example of English and Uzbek languages contributes to clarifying the social factors affecting the development of these languages and the different and similar features of the terminology of the two languages.

Terminology is a science that studies terms and appeared as an independent science in the twentieth century. Terminology has been studied for several centuries as a specific part of the lexical system of a language, but this is seen as only an initial stage. When the study of terms was carried out at the same time as their correction, the study of terms was not yet separated from lexicology.

In the construction of the modern Uzbek literary language, terminology is distinguished by its special place and status. There are two worldviews about the role of terminology in the vocabulary. According to the first idea, terminology is recognized as an independent layer of the lexicon of the literary language, while according to the second theory it is separated from the composition of the vocabulary of the literary language, evaluated as a "separate" object, and types of speech (dialect, slang, lively speech). According to V. P. Danilenko, terminology means an independent functional type of general literary language, i.e. traditional scientific language (language of science, science or technology) [1.8]. The language of science, as one of the functional systems of the general literary language, stands alongside the concepts of the language of live conversation and the language of fiction. The language of science is formed and developed on the basis of the general literary language of the nation.

Therefore, the foundation of the language of science and science is the lexicon, word formation and grammar of the general literary language. According to H. Hewell, terminology is a set of terms related to a specific science or words used in the field of technology. By recording the meaning of the terms, we also record the concepts they represent [2.1967]

There are different understandings of the term. For example, for logicians, a term is a word that refers to a set of descriptions (or descriptions) of a specific object and is applied to it. Any word in any language can be a term. In science and technology, a term is an artificially invented or special word taken from natural language.

The field of application of such a word is specified or limited by representatives of one or another scientific school. Unlike universal terms, terms specific to science and technology are combined into terminological systems as hierarchical units, they achieve their meaning only within the same system, in which a logical (conceptual) terminological field corresponds to them. Any development and progress in science indicates the emergence or clarification of scientific terms. The theory of marked (marked) and unmarked (unmarked) units is considered a new step in the development and improvement of logical division.

The terminological lexicon includes words and phrases that are widely used in the context of non-professional speech, which has moved from the sphere of narrow specialization to the sphere of mass communication. The term that has entered the sphere of universal language is separated from its terminology, terminological field and system, and is separated from the

characteristics of the term. A lot of opinions have been expressed in the scientific literature about the definition of the term. In almost all definitions, the term is described as a word or phrase expressing a special scientific and technical concept.

In the works of D. Lotte, the need to treat the term not as a separate sign, but as a member of a specific system, is emphasized. According to his opinion, the systematic relations in the content plan determine the systematic character of the terminology. The meaning and position of terms in the system of terms is determined by the meaning and position of a certain concept in the system of concepts. Terminology is considered as a set of special concepts, a set of special concepts united in a system of terms, representing a categorical apparatus specific to different schools, scientific directions and specific ideas. In modern linguistics, there are various ideas and points of view regarding the emergence of new terminology, barriers to its implementation, principles and methods of formation. Substantial, functional, derivational, semantic and pragmatic principles of term interpretation are recognized.

According to the representatives of the substantive point of view, a term is a special word or a combination of words, which differs from other nominative units by its unambiguity, accuracy, systematicity, context-free, and emotional neutrality. According to the functional point of view, terms are not special words, but words with a special function; Any word can play the role of the term. The derivational point of view is closely related to the processes of formation of terms. According to the supporters of this idea, the term is recognized not only as a variant of a simple word, but also as a specially made unit with new, unique specific characters. The reasons for the emergence of new terms are evaluated by the need to express new realities.

Certain requirements are imposed on the term, this aspect distinguishes it from ordinary words in the common language and dialects. Nomenclature is a new category of terminology. The nomenclature of any field includes all species names related to this field. When their amount reaches an excessive level, it requires a special structure. For example, trying to give a separate name to each of the more than 200,000 plant species today is useless, it is not even possible. It is necessary to distinguish between the nomenclature of natural sciences, which reflects the stages of human knowledge and understanding of nature, the technical nomenclature that is discovered and created by humans (production nomenclature), as well as the commercial nomenclature, which is specially created for the purpose of providing and selling consumer goods

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